

ISSUES OF COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN TEACHERS IN THE GLOBALIZATION PERIOD.

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Abstract: In this article, the position of any country in the world community is determined by the standard of living of its population and political and economic activity. In today's globalized world, rapid adaptation of the state to the conditions of the international competition process is the main factor of its successful and stable development. The main advantage of highly developed countries in this is related to the availability of opportunities for personal development, which is determined by the state of the education system. The factors that ensure the stable economic growth of the state today and in the future directly depend on the development of the education sector.

Key words: Professional competence, legal democracy, civil society, professional independence, work ethic, emotional stability, education, international competition, professional development.

INTRODUCTION.

Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures new achievements. Although international cooperation in various fields is bearing fruit, strengthening national independence in all aspects, enriching the achieved achievements, quickly eliminating existing shortcomings requires special dedication, enthusiasm, courage and requires persistence.

Therefore, modernization of the educational system - measures such as finding effective mechanisms for educating the young generation, equipping the educational process with modern technologies, renewing it spiritually, structurally technical and technological restructuring. It is a process that includes activities and must be carried out in accordance with the education of a perfect person. For this reason, every educational institution in the republic attaches great importance to improving the quality of the personnel it trains. At a time when nanotechnologies are being created in science and production, the creation of new generation textbooks, the introduction of the module-credit system in education, the implementation of controls in various directions, the use of active teaching methods, and other similar organizational works are expected. pedagogue demands that the personnel acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications in accordance with the requirements of the time. Socio-economic developments in our country today require the modernization of the educational system, its structural reconstruction, changing and updating educational programs taking into account the modern achievements of education, science, technology and technology, economy and culture. envisages

Wide adoption of advanced technologies, integration of continuous education with science and production, introduction of a differentiated approach to education in accordance with the

abilities and capabilities of students, and advanced pedagogical technologies of education and modern education. "the creation of teaching-methodical complexes, the system of organization and management of pedagogical processes improvement is the basis for developing the professional competence of teachers.

In our country, the implementation of the tasks defined in the state program puts new demands on the modern teacher. The question of what a modern teacher should be comes to the fore. The issue of approach from the point of view of competence is not approached as risky as in foreign countries.

Creating pedagogical and psychological conditions for teachers in the field of education, modernizing the content of the process of training teachers of vocational education based on the competence approach, the characteristics of the formation of professional competence and the creative design of educational technologies, and the criteria that determine the level of formation of professional competence The science of "Professional competence" occupies a special place in the study of issues such as justification. In order to improve the education system in our society, the training of qualified personnel for educational institutions has increased their competence to the level of necessity. This means that at present, great attention should be paid to the preparation of specialists who meet the requirements of the times, not only with a deep study of their theoretical knowledge, but also with great human qualities, who are able to engage in communication, and who master their work thoroughly. shows.

Especially, this requirement of the present time once again proves that teachers should be trained as civilized individuals, armed with high pedagogical skills and modern technologies, in order to increase their qualifications and competence. The strategy of psychological-pedagogical training for teacher training is to increase the professional skills, moral image, and intellectual potential of future teachers, based on the current state of spiritual and educational work. It serves to provide coherence and continuity between stages.

In today's globalized world, rapid adaptation of the state to the conditions of the international competition process is the main factor of its successful and stable development. In this regard, the main advantage of highly developed countries is that the state of the educational system depends on the availability of opportunities for personal development. The factors that ensure the stable economic growth of the state today and in the future also depend on the development of the education sector and the training of pedagogical personnel.

Teaching is a profession that has been respected since the beginning of the history of human society. From this point of view, the factors that ensure the stable economic growth of the state today and in the future are directly related to the development of the education sector.

In today's era of globalization, the competence of modern teachers is reflected in:

- humanitarianism;
- communicativeness;
- professional independence, hard work, emotional stability, creative approach to one's work;
- rational use of pedagogical techniques and technologies;
- improvement of speech technique, control of one's voice, facial expressions and body, ability to influence the team and the individual;

- problems in modern science and production, pedagogical,
- to be aware of information and high-level technologies and to apply them to the educational process, etc.

Pedagogical skill and competence is the theoretical level of the professional skills acquired on the basis of flexible skills and creativity in a certain field. Such qualities serve in the formation of professional pride in the process of instilling respect for the chosen profession of young people.

In this regard, it is important for the teacher-educator to have skills in raising a mature generation.

Pedagogical skills and competence are used to give a description of the profession, to acquire the mastery level in the educational process, and to describe the professional qualities in the performance of a certain task in the educational process.

Pedagogical skill and competence require the teacher to research, skill, use pedagogical technologies, organize his activity on a scientific basis.

Therefore, the multifaceted activity of the teacher and his ability, being an excellent artist and selfless, and the issue of educating young people as a well-rounded person is one of the urgent issues at the level of state policy, so teachers should acquire pedagogical skills and competence.

Therefore, pedagogical skill and pedagogical competence are not a standard way of working for all pedagogues, but it is a process that occurs as a result of each teacher's work and creative work. In this regard, in order to develop the competence of pedagogic specialists, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: education, plan pedagogical activities;

- modeling of practical exercises, being able to predict the possibilities of overcoming difficulties, developing a strategy for correcting mistakes;
- all-round development of the learner, education
- acquisition of modern integrative, cognitive activity management methods of education, which help to "live", creative organization of the process;
- effective use of various methods and tools for diagnosing the quality of teaching and education in relation to the new requirements of educational standards and one's own needs, in addition, acquiring the skills of independent creation and control of new methodological ways;
- regularly reading new literature on pedagogy and psychology;
- using advanced pedagogical experiences and modern achievements of the science of pedagogy in practice, conducting spiritual-educational and educational work that forms a creative, independent thinker and a well-rounded person in all respects.
- In this case, the activity of the teacher is expressed in the following:
 - self-development;
 - organization of educational activities based on advanced technologies;
 - creating a basis for mutual cooperation between teachers and students;
 - ensuring the acquisition of the direction of research based on the students' internal motivation of educational activities, etc.

Pedagogical activity implies three types of pedagogical influence on students: what to teach, who to teach and how to teach? Therefore, a skilled teacher can improve learning by selecting material from the subject and dividing it into groups, realizing the available opportunities of

students, the general goals of education, and rationally choosing the forms, methods and methods of influencing students, and should apply.

Naturally, a skilled teacher analyzes his personal activity. During the activity, it is very important to take into account the students' personal work and time spent, to be able to see the places where there are shortcomings in the work and to choose ways to eliminate them, to analyze one's own experience and the work of colleagues. If all the listed components of pedagogical activity are present, then it can be considered psychologically complete and mature.

To develop pedagogical competence, setting pedagogical tasks and goals during the activity, changing it, comparing and classifying pedagogical situations, making decisions, pedagogical thinking and pedagogical intuition, analysis, evaluation, self-correction, pedagogical important professional qualities such as reflection and others are embodied.

The development of pedagogical competence is directly related to the changes, motives, goals, use of new tools, methods and activity program in its activity. Teacher activity is formed on the basis of various pedagogical changes. A teacher with pedagogical skills is an influential leader who is able to overcome difficulties in education, who can understand the inner world of the growing young generation, who can feel their feelings, who skillfully adapts to the personality of a child whose inner world is delicate and vulnerable. cautious a person with wisdom and creative courage, scientific analysis, imagination and fantasy, deep scientific thinking.

Pedagogical skills include pedagogical knowledge and understanding, as well as skills in the field of pedagogical techniques, which allow to achieve more results with less effort in education.

Pedagogical skills and competence are extraordinary energy, determination, diligence, desire to conduct research, adaptability to a new situation, a new team, sincerity, correctness and honesty, sharp intelligence, requires the ability to test one tool against another.

The establishment of an independent, democratic, legal state with a great future will be in the hands of spiritually mature, morally pure young people. Therefore, it is emphasized that attention should be paid to youth education, especially in the social and spiritual sphere:

- commitment to humanitarian ideals;
- loyalty to the idea of national independence;
- restoration of spirituality and morality;
- knowledge and reproduction of ancient and modern cultural assets, literature and art;
- to decide on the rules of freedom of opinion, conscience and religion; implementation of the rules of social justice;
- integrating the national, historical and cultural traditions and spiritual experience of our people into the education and training system;
- development of all types of creativity.

The content of the reforms in the field of education is aimed at educating young people who think freely and independently. In this process, it is necessary to change the "teacher-student" relationship. Conscious discipline should take the place of forced obedience in the relationship between the teacher and the student.

Therefore, another important requirement for a teacher is to deeply understand new pedagogical technologies and teach children to think independently. In a democratic society, children, in general, everyone is raised to think freely.

Therefore, it is necessary to achieve the goals of education, to organize diverse activities of students, to make them loyal to the Motherland, free from evil ideas, educated, polite, faithful, hardworking, free-thinking, conscious. , it is the responsibility of the teacher to grow into a perfect person.

Thus, the development of pedagogical competence in fulfilling the tasks assigned to the education sector by our state is organized through various forms and methods, based on the application of special didactic principles, relying on pedagogical and psychological laws.

Based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the demands of the society, today the student's activity is organized on the basis of learning knowledge, skills and abilities in the educational process. teacher's activity is carried out as a result of setting pedagogical tasks, achieving the goal, determining the subject of activity, means, rationally choosing the methods of their implementation, managing the student's activity, organizing education based on advanced mutual cooperation. increases.

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